

Complications of Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy in Relation to the Normal Anatomy and Variations in the Extrahepatic Biliary Tree and Vascular Anatomy: A Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a common surgical procedure for the management of symptomatic cholelithiasis. However, complications can occur during the surgery, when there are anomalies in the extrahepatic biliary tree and vascular anatomy.

Aim: This study was done to document the complications of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in relation to the normal anatomy and variations in the extrahepatic biliary tree and vascular anatomy.

Material and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery at our hospital. The study duration was of one year. Adult patients who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy for symptomatic cholelithiasis were included. Preoperative workup included a complete history, physical examination, relevant laboratory tests, abdominal ultrasound and CT abdomen and MRCP where required. The surgical procedure followed the standard technique and anomalies in the extrahepatic biliary tree and vascular anatomy were documented. Both intraoperative and postoperative complications and time taken for surgery were recorded.

Results: In a study of 76 patients, anomalies in the extrahepatic biliary tree and vascular anatomy were found in 27.6% of cases. Intraoperative complications occurred in 5.2% of patients, including vascular and bile duct injuries, while postoperative complications were identified in 3.9% of patients. The distribution of patients based on anatomy and complications were documented. The complication rate was higher among patients with anatomical variations, accounting for 19.04% (4 patients out of 21 patients) compared to patients with normal anatomy, where the complication rate was 3.64% (2 out of 55 patients). Overall out of 76 patients, 70 (92.10%) were found to be without complications, while 6 (7.89%) developed overall complications. The calculated p value of 0.02 indicated a statistically significant relationship between anatomy and complications.

Conclusion: This study highlights the importance of understanding the variations in the extrahepatic biliary tree and vascular anatomy during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The presence of anomalies can increase the risk of complications during and after surgery. Accurate identification of the variations in the extrahepatic biliary tree and vascular anatomy are crucial for successful laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Therefore, awareness of these anomalies, which can occur upto 66% can help the surgeon adapt their surgical approach to minimize these.

Keywords: Complications; Vasculobiliary anomalies, Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy.

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Introduction

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a frequent surgical procedure for gallstone diseases, offering advantages like small incisions and faster recovery [1]. However, complications can arise from anatomical variations in the biliary tree and vascular anatomy [2]. Variations include cystic artery, cystic duct length, aberrant right hepatic duct, accessory bile ducts, and anomalous junctions

between common bile duct and pancreatic duct [3]. These variations can increase the risk of injury, bleeding, biliary leaks, prolonged surgery, infections, retained stones and higher costs [4]. Understanding their impact is crucial for surgical planning and patient safety. Pre-operative imaging may not always be feasible, so surgeons rely on experience and intraoperative findings [5].

Proper identification of structures is vital. The critical view of safety technique ensures safe dissection by clarifying vasculo-ductal structures [6]. Variations in biliary and vascular anatomy are more common than the classical description [3]. Many studies reported that the incidence of vasculo biliary anomalies varies from 15 to 66 percent [1].

This study underscores the critical importance of gaining a thorough understanding of the diverse patterns and configurations within the extrahepatic biliary tree and vascular system when undertaking laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Anomalies within these anatomical structures can significantly heighten the risks associated with the surgical procedure, both during its execution and in the postoperative phase.

The precise identification of variations in the extrahepatic biliary tree and vascular anatomy is therefore an absolute necessity for ensuring the success of a laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Consequently, being well-informed about these anomalies which can manifest in as many as 66% of cases, empowers the surgeon to adapt their surgical approach, thereby minimizing potential complications and enhancing patient outcomes.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting: Department of General Surgery.

Study Duration: 1st November 2022-31st October 2023

Study Design: Cross-sectional Study

Ethical Aspects: Institutional ethics committee approval was taken prior to conducting this study

Sample Size: 76 adult patients who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy for symptomatic cholelithiasis were included in this study.

Inclusion Criteria: All adult patients between the ages 18-65 years who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy for symptomatic cholelithiasis

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Perforated gall bladder
2. Previous abdominal surgery
3. Carcinoma of the gall bladder
4. Choledocholithiasis
5. American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) grade 3 or above

Preoperative Workup: Complete history and physical examination, relevant laboratory tests, abdominal ultrasound in all cases and Contrast Enhanced Computed Tomography (CECT abdomen)/ Magnetic Resonance Cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) where required.

Data analysis:

The data was entered and imported into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0 for statistical analysis. Qualitative data was analysed by applying frequency and percentage while quantitative data was analysed by mean and standard deviation. Appropriate statistical tests were applied based on the distribution and type of data. $P < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results

76 patients who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy was meticulously studied to assess the presence of biliary and vascular anomalies, intra and post-operative complications and duration of surgery. In the present study vasculobiliary anomalies were detected in 27.6% of cases. Partially intrahepatic gallbladder was the most prevalent accounting for 3.9% (3 out of 76 patients).

Additionally, completely intrahepatic gallbladder (Figure-1) and duplication of gallbladder/bilobed gallbladder were less common, each observed in only 1 out of 76 patients, constituting 1.3% of the population. Furthermore, Phrygian cap anomaly represented 2.6% of the sample. (Table 1) The cystic artery was positioned anterior to the cystic duct in 1 patient, constituting 1.3% of the sample. Additionally, a short cystic artery was identified in another patient, also representing 1.3% of the population and 3.9% patients exhibited Moynihan's hump. (Table 2, Figure-2)

The most common biliary anomaly observed was the short cystic duct, which was present in 5.2% of the patients. (Figure-3) The long cystic duct anomaly was identified in three patients, representing 3.9% of the total sample. Additionally, there was one patient, constituting 1.3% of the sample, with a cystic duct parallel to the common bile duct. Similarly, one patient was noted to have a double cystic duct or accessory duct, also representing 1.3% of the total sample. (Table 3, Figure-4)

In the intraoperative phase, vascular injury was reported in one patient with anomaly of short cystic artery constituting 1.3% of the total sample, while no vascular injuries occurred in patients with normal anatomy. Similarly, bile duct injury was observed in one patient with biliary anomaly due to short cystic duct also representing 1.3% of the total sample. Gallbladder perforation was noted in one patient with normal anatomy and one patient with anomalous intrahepatic gallbladder.

During the immediate post-operative phase, bile leak occurred in 1.3% of the total sample probably due to accessory bile duct seen intraoperatively. Patient was followed up and the bile leak subsided. In contrast, bleeding was reported in one patient

with normal anatomy and one patient with biliary anomalies, resulting in a total of 2 cases and comprising 2.6% of the total sample. (Table-4) In summary, amongst the 21 patients with biliary anomalies, a total of 4 complications were encountered, while among the 55 patients with normal anatomy, 2 complications were ob-

served. Over all out of 76 patients, 70 (92.10%) were found to be without complications, while 6 (7.89%) developed overall complications. The calculated p value of 0.02 indicated a statistically significant relationship between anatomy and complications.

Table 1: Anomalies of the gallbladder

Anomalies of gall bladder	No. of patients (n=76)	Percentage
Partially Intrahepatic	3	3.9%
Completely Intrahepatic gallbladder	1	1.3%
Duplication of gallbladder/ bilobed gallbladder	1	1.3%
Phrygian cap	2	2.6%

Table 2: Vascular anomalies

Type of vascular anomaly	No. of patients (n=76)	Percentage
Cystic artery anterior to cystic duct	1	1.3%
Short cystic artery	1	1.3%
Moynihan's hump	3	3.9%

Table 3: Anomalies of the extrahepatic biliary tree

Biliary anomalies	No. of patients(n=76)	Percentage
Short Cystic duct	4	5.2%
Long Cystic duct	3	3.9%
Cystic duct parallel to Common bile duct	1	1.3%
Double cystic duct/ Accessory duct	1	1.3%

Table 4: Complications associated to anomalies

		Anomalies (n=21)	Normal anatomy(n=55)	Total(n=76)	Grand total	p-value
Intraoperative	Vascular injury	1	-	1(1.3%)	4(5.3%)	
	Bile duct injury	1	-	1(1.3%)		
	Gallbladder perforation	1	1	2(3.6%)		
Immediate post-operative	Bile leak	1	-	1(1.3%)	3(3.9%)	
	Bleeding	1	1	2(2.6%)		
Total		5	2	7	9.21%	0.02

P Value = 0.02. There was significant number of complications in patients with anatomical variations.

Figure-1: Intrahepatic gallbladder

Figure-2: Short cystic artery originating from caterpillar right hepatic hump

Figure-3: Short cystic duct

Figure-4: Accessory duct of luschka

Discussion

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy has emerged as a safe and effective treatment for multiple gallbladder diseases due to its advantages. However, despite its advantages, it is not free from complications. These complications are more commonly associated with variations in the extrahepatic biliary tree and vascular anatomy, which can vary considerably between individuals. It is important to have a good understanding of the vasculo biliary anatomy and any potential variants while performing laparoscopic cholecystectomy in order to prevent injury to the vasculobiliary tree during the procedure. While pre-operative assessment of the biliary anatomy is ideal, it may not always be possible or practical [2].

In our study, we reported a 3.9% incidence of intraoperative complications amongst anomalies and 1.3% incidence amongst cases with normal anatomy. This aligns with existing literature, including studies by Larobina et al. and McKinley et al., who reported complication rates ranging from 0.5% to 6% which is similar to our study [3,4]. Frilling et al. and Singh et al. reported that the incidence of vascular injury is 0.04-1.22% while that of biliary injury is 0.1-0.6% [5,6]. In our study vascular injury due to anomolus short cystic artery was reported in 1.3% while bile duct injury was also reported in 1.3 % of the population due to

short cystic duct which was higher as compared to other studies as we had lesser sample size.

However, we observed a lower incidence of gallbladder perforation of 2.6% compared to the broader literature as highlighted by Duca et al [7]. Immediate post-operative complication of bile leak was seen in 1.3% which could be probably due to bile duct injury intraoperatively. The most common cause of post-operative bile leak of the population in our study which is lesser than the study by Radunovic et al with an incidence of 1.8% [8].

Nevertheless, our study's reported average operative time of 60 minutes, as supported by Subhash et alis consistent with existing research [9].

Studies suggest that most patients having undergone elective uncomplicated laparoscopic cholecystectomy can be safely discharged after 24 postoperative hours and in some cases, discharge on the same day can be considered [10]. In our study we discharged majority of our patients 96.0% within post-operative day 2 as we had minimal complications.

Thus, there was a significant number of complications in patients with anatomical variations as the p value is <0.05 in our study which is against the study by Katti SC et al. who

conducted study amongst 80 patients on variations of the vascular and extrahepatic biliary system in laparoscopic cholecystectomy and its associated outcomes [11].

Conclusion

This study highlights the critical role of identifying and addressing anatomical variations in laparoscopic cholecystectomy to mitigate the risk of complications and enhance surgical outcomes. Surgeon should adapt their approach based on patient factors and anatomical variations to ensure optimal results. Continued emphasis on thorough preoperative evaluation, intraoperative techniques and postoperative monitoring is crucial for refining surgical practices and improving patient care in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Further research should focus on refining imaging techniques and surgical strategies to better manage anatomical variations and minimize complications in this patient population.

References

1. Al-Sayigh HA. The Incidence of Cystic Artery Variation during Laparoscopic Surgery. *Med J Babylon*. 2010; 7(4): 389-403.6
2. Hamza MU, Jaffar AA, Hassan HA, et al. Vascular and gallbladder variation in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Med J Babylon*. 2008; 5(1):119-34.
3. Larobina M, Nottle P. Complete evidence regrading major vascular injuries during laparoscopic access. *Surg laparosc Endosc Percutan Tech*. 2005; 15:119-23. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/01.sle.0000166967.49274.ca> PMID:15956893
4. Mc Kinley SK, Brunt LM, Schwaitzberg SD. Prevention of bile injury: the case for incorporating educational theories of expertise. *Surg Endosc*. 2014; 28:3385-91. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00464-014-3605-8> PMID:24939158.
5. Frilling A, Li J, Weber F, Fruhans NR et al. Major bile duct injuries after laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a tertiary center experience. *J Gastrointes Surg*. 2004; 8:679-85. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gassur.2004.04.005> PMID:15358328
6. Singh K, Ohri A. Anatomic landmarks: their usefulness in safe laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Surg Endosc*. 2006; 20:1754-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00464-005-0528-4> PMID:17001444
7. Duca S, Bala O, Al-Hajjar N, Iancu C, Puja IC, Munteanu D, Graur F. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy: incidents and complications. A retrospective analysis of 9542 consecutive laparoscopic operations HPB (Oxford). 2003; 5:152-58.
8. Radunovic, Miodrag et al. "Complications of Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy: Our Experience from a Retrospective Analysis." *Open access Macedonian journal of medical sciences* vol. 4, 4 (2016): 641-6.
9. Subhas, Gokulakrishna et al. "Prolonged (longer than 3 hours) laparoscopic cholecystectomy: reasons and results." *The American surgeon* vol. 77,8 (2011): 981-4
10. Psaila J, Agrawal S, Fountain U, Whitfi eld T, Murgatroyd B, Dunsire MF, et al. Day-surgery laparoscopic cholecystectomy: factors influencing same-day discharge. *World J Surg*. 2008; 32(1):76-81. DOI: 10.1007/s00268-007-9225-x
11. Katti SC, Dwivedi S, Nagula BP. Study on variations of the vascular and extrahepatic biliary system in laparoscopic cholecystectomy and its associated outcomes. *European Journal of Cardiovascular Medicine*. 2023 Jul 1; 13(3).